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An Efficient Protocol for Isolation of Genomic DNA From Leaf Tissues of Mulberry Plant (*Morus Spp.*) Using CTAB Method

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Abstract:

Isolation of genomic DNA is the first and foremost step in any type of molecular study. The purity of DNA is very crucial for success of genomic studies. Since mulberry (*Morus spp.*) have high phenolic content, it becomes difficult to isolate fairly pure DNA which hinders the results of molecular studies. In present experiment an attempt has been made to develop an efficient and cost effective protocol for isolation of DNA from mulberry leaves. The quality of DNA was observed on gel electrophoresis, and purity of DNA as revealed on spectrophotometer by ratios of absorbance at 260/280nm was closer to 2.0, which indicated the presence of fairly pure DNA. Genomic DNA was analysed for PCR amplification with SSR markers further confirmed its purity

Keywords: Mulberry, DNA, protocol, electrophoresis, spectrophotometer, SSR markers

Introduction:

Mulberry plant (*Morus spp.*) has its unique importance as its leaves forms the sole food material for mulberry silkworm *Bombyx mori* L. Each and every part of mulberry plants has remarkable medicinal properties. Thus, mulberry has always attracted the interest of scientists. Morphology and reproductive studies on mulberry are essential for mulberry breeders to classify different genotypes to evolve promising varieties for commercial exploitation. It is a known fact that plants selected on the basis of phenotypic traits alone may not always give the desired results because the phenotypic traits are highly influenced by environmental conditions. Hence, genetically reliable marker systems like molecular markers are increasingly being used to assess the genetic diversity and other parameters among most of the crop plants, including mulberry.

In India, hundreds of collections of diverse mulberry accessions whose genotypic status is unknown. By making use of the molecular marker technology based on PCR approach, diverse accessions of mulberry can be made a possible and good number of mulberry genotypes can be accessed. However, very scanty studies have been made to understand the genetic variability among genotypes for selecting potential parental material for breeding purposes. Molecular markers are useful complements to morphological and phenological characters because they are plentiful, independent of tissue or environmental effects and allow accession identification in the early stages of development.

Isolation of genomic DNA is the first and foremost step in any type of molecular study. The purity of DNA is very crucial for success of genomic studies. Many contaminating agents including polyphenolic compounds, resins, latex, and polysaccharides may be present in the cell which hinders the isolation of DNA and interfere with its quality and experimental results. Time to time many protocols has been introduced for genomic DNA isolation from mulberry plant tissues. Here an attempt has been made to isolate good quality DNA which was further got confirmed with SSR markers that yielded good results and revealed polymorphism in the studied genotypes.

Material and methods:

The locale of the study:

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The present experiment was carried out at Division of Sericulture, Udheywala in collaboration with School of Biotechnology, Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology of Jammu, Chatha.

Collection of leaf samples:

Leaf samples of the selected varieties were collected from mulberry germplasm bank maintained at Division of Sericulture, SKUAST –J, Udheywala campus from bush plantation maintained at 1x1 meter distance. The samples were collected in the early morning before sunrise and carried to laboratory at School of Biotechnology, SKUAST-J, Chatha in icebox having ice packs and stored in – 20 °C in deep freezer for further process.

Genomic DNA extraction:

Total genomic DNA was isolated using the modified CTAB (Cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide) protocol by Doyle and Doyle (1990). Young leaves were harvested randomly from selected plants of each genotype (approximately 5-7g of fresh weight). Harvested leaves were placed in poly bags and stored in ice. One ml of extraction buffer was poured in 2 ml Eppendorf tubes and incubated at 65°C in the water bath.

Plate 1.1: Leaf Sample

Plate 1.2: Powdered Sample

Plate 1.3: DNA pallet

Plate 1: Genomic DNA isolation

- Fresh leaf material was taken, and about 500 mg of leaf lamina was grounded to fine powder using prechilled pestle and mortar after adding liquid nitrogen to make leaves brittle as well as to stop DNase activity.
- The powder was transferred immediately to 1 ml of pre-warmed extraction buffer and incubated in a water bath at 65°C for 35 minutes with occasional stirring.
- An equal volume of phenol: chloroform (1: 1) was added to the tubes and tilted for 10 minutes. The samples were centrifuged for 15 minutes at 10,000 rpm.
- The supernatant was then transferred to a fresh tube and again treated with Phenol: chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1), mixed slowly for 10 minutes and centrifuged.
- To the supernatant, chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (24:1) was added and centrifuged. 0.6 volume of chilled Isopropanol was added to the tubes and stored at 4°C for 1-2 hours.
- Centrifugation was done at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was discarded, and pellets were washed with 0.01 M ammonium acetate (200 µl-300 µl) to remove contamination.
- 0.6 volume of Iso-propanol was added for precipitation, and centrifugation was done at 5,000 rpm for 10 minutes.
- The pellets were washed with 70 percent ethanol and air dried.
- DNA was dissolved in 200 µl of TE buffer and stored at 4°C.

RNase Treatment:

- For purification of DNA, 300 µl of RNase (10mg/ml) was added to the samples and incubated for 1 hour at 37°C in a water bath.
- An equal volume of Phenol: Chloroform: Isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1) was added, tilted for 10 minutes and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes.
- To the supernatant collected in another tube, 0.6 volume of chilled Iso-propanol was added and centrifuged to get a pellet.
- DNA pellet was washed with 70 percent ethanol, air dried, dissolved in 125 µl of TE (Tris-cl, EDTA) buffer and stored at -20°C for further use.

DNA quantification:

The concentration of the genomic DNA was estimated using Agrose gel electrophoresis and UV Spectrophotometric method.

Agarose gel electrophoresis

Quantity of DNA was detected by agarose gel electrophoresis. 0.8 g of agarose was dissolved in 100 ml of 1X TBE electrophoresis buffer.

- The mixture was heated till the agarose dissolved completely and cooled down to 60°C with constant stirring.
- Ethidium bromide was added to a final concentration of 0.5 µg/ml of buffer.
- Agarose solution was poured into an already prepared gel mould with combs and was left for 20-30 minutes for solidification.
- DNA samples for loading were prepared by adding 2µl loading dye (6X) to 3µl DNA.
- DNA samples were loaded into wells with the help of micropipette.
- The gel was run for about 1-2 hours at 80 V/cm and visualized under gel documentation system, and DNA samples were photographed.

The intensity of fluorescence of each sample was compared with that of 100 bp molecular ladder, and then the DNA concentration of each sample was ascertained. The quality of DNA samples was determined based on whether DNA formed a single high molecular weight band (good quality) or a smear (degraded or poor quality).

3.3.5 UV Spectrophotometric method

The optical density of DNA samples was measured at 260nm and 280nm using spectrophotometer (Peg-Lab Nanodrop). The ratio between 1.8 and 2.0 showed the presence of fairly pure DNA. The value less than 1.8 indicated the presence of protein contaminants and value greater than 1.8 indicated the presence of RNA.

Results and discussion:

DNA Quantification

Pure DNA samples were subjected to DNA quantification to know the concentration of genomic DNA through agarose gel electrophoresis and Nanodrop. The concentration of genomic DNA varied from 100.22 to 981.70 ng/µl, and absorbance ranged from 1.6 to 2.0 (Table 1).

Table 1: Concentration of genomic DNA (ng/μl)

S.No.	Genotype	DNA concentration (ng/μl)	Absorbance (A _{260/280})
1.	BC-259	137.53	1.6
2.	Tr-10	433.28	1.7
3.	Kanva-2	380.62	1.7
4.	S-799	187.58	1.8
5.	C-763	659.29	1.8
6.	Asayuki	597.37	1.7
7.	Fukushima	298.65	1.8
8.	Kamabori	716.11	1.7
9.	Chakmajra	100.22	1.8
10.	Behrampur	571.70	1.7
11.	S-1	291.26	1.7
12.	Sujanpur	185.33	1.7
13.	Goshyerami	120.68	1.8
14.	Kokuso-20	810.65	1.7
15.	Kairyoroso	119.13	1.8
16.	Enshutukasuka	267.38	1.8
17.	Rokokyoso	115.07	1.8
18.	Kokuso-27	442.32	2.0
19.	Shimanouchi	720.66	1.7
20.	NS-2	216.90	1.7
21.	NS-1	718.85	1.6
22.	NS-3	209.28	1.8
23.	Limeneina	208.28	1.8
24.	KNG	490.97	1.7
25.	Chinese white	174.92	1.8
26.	Ichinose	902.52	1.8
27.	S-41	819.75	1.7
28.	S-54	126.73	1.7
29.	T-1	180.86	1.7
30.	Tr-4	107.58	1.8
31.	Tr-8	121.44	1.8
32.	LF-1	132.08	1.8
33.	LF-2	157.93	1.8
34.	S-36	823.57	1.7
35.	S-30	173.78	1.7
36.	Miuraso	940.69	1.9
37.	Dal local	577.07	1.7
38.	Bhrem C-776	981.70	1.8
39.	S-1608	970.79	1.8
40.	S-1635	117.98	1.8
41.	V-1	248.31	1.9
42.	S-146	185.28	1.8
43.	S-1708	236.41	1.8
44.	S-1531	404.40	1.7

PCR amplification of SSR primers:

Five SSR makers, namely Mul3SS80, Mul3SSR97, Mul3SSR122, SS05, and M6 were used for PCR based amplification which clearly indicated the genetic diversity in the genotypes with respect to target loci.

SSR-PCR banding profile

The amplified products were subjected to electrophoretic separation using horizontal agrose gel electrophoresis. 3 percent agrose gel was prepared in 1X TBE buffer stained with ethidium bromide. In each PCR tubes 3μl of loading dye was added and mixed well and then loaded to separate wells. 100 bp DNA ladder was used as a molecular weight marker for determining the molecular weights of SSR based PCR bands. Electrophoresis was carried out at 80 V for 3 hours. The gel was examined under UV and documented using gel

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documentation system. Sufficient amplification was observed in all the studied genotypes with slight variation in intensity of the amplified bands. Primer Mul3SSR80 produced amplification at 140 bp, Mul3SSR97 at 292 bp, Mul3SSR122 at 219 bp, SS05 at 350 bp and M6 at 310 bp (Fig. 2-5).

The method described here could isolate a good amount of high quality DNA, which was evident from spectrophotometric analysis, PCR amplification. The major modifications in the present study from the standard Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide (CTAB) protocol (Doyle and Doyle, 1990) are concentrations and volumes of reagents and solutions used and time devoted at each step. However, Anuradha *et al.* (2013) utilized Silver Staining of Polyacrylamide Gel for confirmation of results. The spectrophotometric analysis at A260/ 280 gave a ratio ranging from 1.6 to 2.0 which was in the range of 1.74 to 1.95 as studied by Anuradha *et al.* (2013) and 2.0-2.2 by Arruda *et al.* (2017). It also included RNase treatment for removal of RNA contamination. The results were further got confirmed by PCR based SSR markers which yielded enough polymorphism. This modified protocol omits the time consuming and hectic steps which supported the use of simple laboratory equipment for yielding good results as earlier suggested by Allen *et al.* (2006), Youssef *et al.* (2015) and Tiwari *et al.* (2017).

Plate 2: Showing PCR amplification of Mul3SSR80 at 140 bp

1- BC-259	2- Tr-10	3- Kanva-2	4- S-799	5-C-763	6- Asayuki
7-Fukushima	8- Kamabori	9-Chakmajra	10- Behrampur	11- S-1	12- Sujanpur
13- Goshyerami	14- Kokuso-20	15- Kairyoroso	16- Enshutukasuka	17- Rokokyoso	
18- Kokuso-27	19- Shimanouchi	20- NS-2	21- NS-1	22- NS-3	23- Limencina
24- KNG	25- Chinese white	26- Ichinose	27- S-41	28- S-54	29-Tr-1
30- Tr-4	31- Tr-8	32- LF-1	33- LF-2	34- S-35	34- S-30
36- Miuraso	37- Dal local	38- Bhrem C-776	39- S-1608	40- S-1635	41- V-1
42- S-146	43- S-1708 and	44- S-1531.			

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Plate 3: Showing PCR amplification of Mul3SSR197 at 180 bp

Plate 4: Showing PCR amplification of Mul3SSR122 at 219 bp

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Plate 5: Showing PCR amplification of SS05 at 350 bp

Plate 6: Showing PCR amplification of M6 at 310 bp

Conclusion:

The present protocol is suitable for isolating high quality DNA from mulberry leaves containing higher amounts of polysaccharides, polyphenols, resins, and other viscous contaminants. The successful amplification of microsatellite markers confirmed the purity of the DNA. This protocol is simple, rapid, inexpensive and easily amenable to other closely related species.

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